

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Elevating the teaching journey: A review on spiritual intelligence and metacognitive awareness in teaching experience

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Abstract

This study analyzes how to contribute spiritual intelligence (SI) and metacognitive awareness (MA) to enhancing teaching experiences and holistic development among educators. It has been established that teachers' emotional resilience, ethical responsibility, and general well-being are improved by spiritual intelligence, which can be defined as profound self-awareness, moral grounding, and the ability to create meaning and purpose. In the meantime, self-reflection, flexibility, and instructional preparation are developed by metacognitive awareness, which is the ability to pay attention, control, and evaluate one's own cognitive processes. The investigation, which draws on a number of research emphasizes how SI and MA both separately and together assist professional development, successful teaching, and enjoyable classroom dynamics. While teachers with good metacognitive abilities are better able to apply evidence-based tactics and adapt flexibly to classroom issues, those with high levels of spiritual intelligence also tend to exhibit higher empathy, integrity, and value-driven approach to teaching.

Keywords: Spiritual Intelligence; Metacognitive Awareness; Teaching Experience; Ethical and Moral Responsibility; Educators' Well-being.

1. Introduction

"Spirituality is the power of the soul. It is the awareness of the spirit beyond the mind and body and the ability to apply this wisdom in life" (Swami Vivekananda, 1898).

Along with teaching experience, there are many characteristics of its as temperament, leadership, attitude and vision of life that's are merely adjoined with spiritual intelligence and it is the basic capability of the teaching-learning process. Being able to apply spiritual information to enhance regular life and well-being has been characterized as spiritual intelligence, which gives us a purposeful and meaningful life (Emmons, 2000). Further, spiritual intelligence was defined by Zohar and Marshall (2000) as the ability to access higher meanings, values and targets for the purpose of direct actions and maintaining internal and external peace. If considered entirely, these definitions present spiritual intelligence as a significant source of existential understanding as well as effective tools to improve human efficiency. In order to defeat the limitations of conventional intelligence models, the concept of spiritual intelligence emerged, accentuating the value of transcendence, deeper meaning and links with human growth (King, 2008). Because it fosters resilience, moral behavior, holistic development and increased life satisfaction, it is crucial (Vaughan, 2002; Wigglesworth, 2011). Nonetheless, there are challenges with operationalizing and quantifying spiritual intelligence, arguments over definitions and issues about cultural and theological biases in its use (Vaughan, 2002). On the other

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hand, to teach successfully, spirituality is more important because through purposeful teaching, value education, ethical development, and moral judgment, the meaningful lives of students can grow (Bansal, 2007).

Ancient Indian texts such as the Bhagavad Gita and Upanishads emphasize self-awareness (atma-bodha) and self-regulation (yoga), which nearly align with the modern psychological comprise of metacognition. However, the word “Metacognition” was first used by John Flavell in 1979. “Cognition about one’s own cognition” is how they put it. Metacognitive awareness means to an own’s distinct ability to monitor, control and examine their cognitive processes. It’s an awareness of one’s self-learning process, matter-resolving techniques, and self-regulation skills (Flavell, 1979). Metacognition mostly has two parts. One is ‘metacognitive knowledge’ (understanding one’s own thinking processes); another is ‘metacognitive regulation’ (controlling and directing one’s own cognitive activities) (Schraw & Dennison, 1994). Declarative, procedural and conditional information about one’s own cognitive process are all included in metacognitive knowledge. In contrast, metacognitive control entails organizing, observing and assessing one’s learning methods. These aspects are especially important in the classroom, where increased metacognitive awareness benefits both teachers and students. When we are concerned about metacognition with teaching experience, it will be a matter of classroom organizing knowledge, managerial power, evaluating competency, which enhance teachers’ professional lives through students’ development (Sahoo & Behera,2021). Based on much research, teachers who have an extended level of metacognitive knowledge they are better able to impose their interesting teaching style and instructional strategies that’s help students become independent thought person (Veenman, Van Hout-Wolters, & Afflerbach, 2006). Furthermore, teachers may foster a metacognitive culture that encourages deeper learning situation in classroom through modeling metacognitive techniques, such as thinking aloud while solving problems or encouraging students to reflect (Artzt & Armour-Thomas, 1992).

Teaching experience has many facets incipency encircling pedagogical content knowledge, evaluation of students, classroom direction serves as a basis of educators’ professional development among different disciplines. In terms of enriching complex thinking, dispose critical problems, effective communication, and promoting self-learning in students, professional development is effectively crucial for teachers (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). The assortment of practical teaching experiences permits teachers to expurgate their instructional strategies, accommodate various learning processes, and grow a deeper understanding of the nuances innate in the teaching and learning process (Rout & Behera, 2014).

2. Relation Between Spiritual Intelligence and Metacognitive Awareness

Spiritual intelligence has a strong relation with reflective thinking, which is a core pattern of metacognitive awareness (King & DeCicco, 2009). MA is the positive prediction of SI, and SI engage individuals by introspective cognitive regulation.

2.1. In relation to self-awareness

- SI comprises deep self-awareness about ethical and moral identity.
- MA comprises self-awareness about own perception and thinking process.

2.2. In relation to thinking and regulation

- SI enhances behavioral processes as such as meaning, values, and purpose.
- MA enhances the regulated thinking process.

3. Role of Spiritual Intelligence in Teaching Experience

In teaching experience, spiritual intelligence has a profound impact. How spiritual intelligence enhances teaching experience and its various dimensions are discussed below.

3.1. Spiritual Intelligence and Teaching Effectiveness

Spiritual intelligence always improved teachers’ performance and by performance growth they impart better knowledge to the students (Gek, Anak & Nengha, 2018). Spiritual intelligence has a positive relationship with teaching effectiveness. High scores in spiritual intelligence indicate a high level of teaching effectiveness and gender, marital status do moderate the relationship between spiritual intelligence and teacher effectiveness (Jabeen, 2020). The performance of teachers is initially related to spiritual intelligence. With higher spiritual teachers tend to perform better, work with responsibility and calmness in teaching (Rahmawati, Ahmad, and Suriansyah, 2019). Spiritual intelligence has no indirect effects on teaching competences and it was also found that spiritual intelligence has the

weakest effect on teaching effectiveness (Sing, 2014). Highly spiritual intelligence teachers more competent in teaching and their teaching profession than the low-level spiritual intelligence teachers of secondary school in South Bengal (Talukdar and Ghosh, 2017). Teachers who have high spiritual intelligence can reframe the teaching content and think about a wider context. Spiritual intelligence can enhance the teaching competencies as well as the teaching profession (George and Visvam, 2013). Spiritual intelligence has a positive effect on teachers' performance and it increase managerial ability and teaching style of teachers (Timang, Nadek and Sihotang, 2021).

3.2. Spiritual Intelligence and Educators' Well-being

Spiritual intelligence has profound effects on teachers' well-being, it enhances self-awareness, transcendence, meaning-making and a deep sense of connectedness which helps to reduce stress and helps to maintain mental health among educators (Vaughan, 2002). Spiritual intelligence helps educators to enhance resilience, emotional balance, and internal peace which develop to fight stress (Amram & Dryer, 2008). Additionally, spirituality improves teachers' empathy, moral judgement and feeling of purpose in life (King & DeCicco, 2009). Moreover, teachers with higher spiritual intelligence often report greater levels of life satisfaction and work engagement, as they perceive their role as a vocation rather than merely a profession (Emmons, 2000).

3.3. Spiritual Intelligence and Professional Development

Spiritual intelligence performs a crucial role in professional development by projecting self-control. Persons with high level spirituality highlight better leadership qualities, enhanced interpersonal relationship, and a better sense of purpose in their careers (Emmons, 2000). Thus, through spiritual intelligence in a professional growth plan can lead to better understanding and sustainable professional advancements (Amram & Dryer, 2008).

3.4. Spiritual Intelligence and Ethical and Moral Responsibility

Ethical and moral awareness are the most necessary things in the teaching profession. By high level spiritual intelligence teachers can uplift their ethical values like integrity, fairness, and justice in the teaching-learning process. Teachers are moral role models for students and they inculcate ethical decision-making power in students, spirituality helps also in these situations (Sisk, 2016).

4. Role of Metacognitive Awareness in Teaching Experience

In teaching experience, metacognitive awareness has a profound impact. How metacognitive awareness enhances teaching experience and its various dimensions is discussed below.

4.1. Metacognitive Awareness and Teaching Effectiveness

With highly metacognitive awareness teachers enable to do their better equipped plan, monitor, and adjust their instructional strategies competently than other teachers. Metacognitive awareness helps to manage educational complexity and dynamic thoughts of teachers to teach effectively (Hughes, 2017). Metacognitive awareness has a positive relation with teaching and teaching competency among secondary prospective teachers. Through enhancing metacognitive awareness teaching competency can lead to improvement (Sahoo, Behera and Sahu, 2021). Teachers' metacognitive skills enhance students' engagement and achievement in education (Phillips, McElwain and Clemmer, 2016). Metacognitive interventions like brainstorming, concept mapping and self-assessment skills have highly positive effects on the teaching and learning process (Meher, Baral and Bhuyan, 2021). Teachers' metacognition hikes their instructional abilities and enhances higher-order thinking and teaching strategies (Nordin & Yunus, 2020).

4.2. Metacognitive Awareness and Educators' Well-being

Teachers' work pressure affected their well-being and it increased stress and burnout. In that situation, metacognition helps to reduce stress and enhance quality of life. Metacognition also promotes psychological well-being (Iacolino et. al. 2023). By understanding their cognitive and emotional responses to challenges, educators can develop a growth mindset that enhances their professional well-being (Dweck, 2006). Metacognitive awareness fosters emotional resilience by helping educators recognize their thought patterns, regulate emotions, and adopt coping strategies (Efklides, 2008). Teachers who have metacognitive skills have controlling power over stress management and leading good well-being in life (Richards, 2012).

4.3. Metacognitive Awareness and Professional Development

The teachers who reflect on their instructional decisions can demonstrate greater innovation and they are flexible about their pedagogical approaches (Schon, 2017). Additionally, metacognitive training programs have the power to enhance

teachers' strength to assess their students' outcomes and teaching proficiency (Baird, 1990). To conjoin metacognitive training into teachers' training programs it significantly enhances teachers' well-being and instructional effectiveness. Teaching quality can be improved by the uses of metacognitive skills such as self-questioning, reflective journals and peer feedback (Brown et. al., 1983).

4.4. Metacognitive Awareness and Instructional Effectiveness

The teachers who have better quality in metacognitive reflection can develop better instructional strategies (Veenman, Van Hout-Wolters, & Afflerbach, 2006). By monitoring their own teaching style and students feedback, teachers can adjust lesson plans, supply clear explanations, and implement teaching strategies based by evidence (Pintrich, 2002).

Table 1 Summary Table: Role of Spiritual Intelligence and Metacognitive Awareness in Teaching Experiences

Dimensions	Spiritual Intelligence	Metacognitive Awareness
Teaching Effectiveness	<p>Positive correlation with teaching effectiveness (Jabeen, 2020).</p> <p>Increase calmness and responsibility in teaching (Rahmawati et al., 2019).</p> <p>No direct effects and it has weakest effects on teaching effectiveness (Sing, 2014).</p> <p>Enhance competency in teaching (Talukdar and Ghosh, 2017).</p> <p>Promotes ability of wider context thinking and content framing (George and Visvam, 2013).</p> <p>Increase managerial abilities, instructional knowledge of instructors (Timang, Nadek and Sihotang, 2021).</p>	<p>Helps to manage educational complexity and dynamics thoughts of teachers to teach effectively (Hughes, 2017).</p> <p>Enhance teaching competency (Sahoo et al., 2021).</p> <p>Increase capabilities of students' engagement in classroom (Phillips et al., 2016).</p> <p>Positive effects on teaching learning process (Meher et al., 2021).</p> <p>Promotes higher order thinking and teaching strategies (Nordin & Yunus, 2020).</p>
Educators' well-being	<p>Enhance self-awareness and transcendent to maintain mental health (Vaughan, 2002).</p> <p>Helps to educators to enhance resilience, emotional balance, and internal for stress reduction (Amram & Dryer, 2008).</p> <p>Encourages empathy and ethical sense (King & DeCicco, 2009).</p> <p>Boost life satisfaction and work engagement (Emmons, 2000).</p>	<p>Foster resilience by reduces stress (Iacolino et al., 2023).</p> <p>Develop growth mindset to enhance professional well-being (Dweck, 2006).</p> <p>Fosters emotional resilience by understanding thought patterns and emotional control (Efklides, 2008).</p> <p>Helps controlling power of stress management and leading good wellbeing of life (Richards, 2012).</p>
Professional Development	<p>Enhance leadership qualities, interpersonal relationship and better sense of purposeful careers (Emmons, 2000).</p> <p>Better understanding and sustainable professional advancements (Amram & Dryer, 2008).</p>	<p>Project innovative thought and flexible pedagogical approaches (Schon, 2017).</p> <p>Enhance teachers' strength to assess their students' outcomes and teaching proficiency (Baird, 1990).</p> <p>Improved by imparts metacognitive skills such as self-questioning, reflective journal and peer feedback (Brown, et. al., 1983).</p>
Ethical and Moral responsibility	<p>Uplift ethical values like integrity, fairness, and justice in teaching learning process. (Sisk, 2016).</p>	
Instructional Effectiveness		<p>Helps to developed better instructional strategies (Veenman, et al., 2006).</p> <p>Enhance experiences to adjust lesson plans, supply clear explanations, and implement teaching strategies by evidence based (Pintrich, 2002).</p>

5. Conclusion

It is concluded that from the several studies, Spiritual Intelligence and Metacognitive Awareness in relation to teaching effectiveness, teachers' well-being, professional development, and ethical factors foster a holistic education and dynamic growth among teachers and students. Spiritual intelligence imparts a deep sense of purpose, an ethical base, and emotional satisfaction, and it ultimately uplifts teaching effectiveness and personal identity in life. On the other hand, metacognitive awareness furnishes educators with planning strategies, instructional development, and cognitive or reflective tools, empowering them to make a positive classroom environment and flexible learning process.

These two factors collectively enrich not only teachers' performance but also enhance the quality of education. Where spiritual intelligence grounds teaching in values, meaning and internal control, metacognitive awareness contributes to evidence-based practice, innovation and cognitive mapping. It is evidently said that spiritual intelligence and metacognitive awareness play a critical and profound role in developing teachers' and students' personalities as well as rising impact in overall education systems.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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